

Low-carbon Transition Processes and their Reading of Justice: The Case of the Scenarios for a Low-Carbon Belgium

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Abstract

Low-carbon transition processes can not only exacerbate existing social inequalities, but also create unprecedented forms of inequality. These social impacts can potentially combine and reinforce each other to create double or even triple vulnerabilities. With a view to ensuring a just transition, it is essential to consider social justice issues in the design of low-carbon strategies. The objective of the present paper is to explore whether and how low-carbon transition processes take into account these issues. It aims to identify and analyze low-carbon transition processes' sensitivity to vulnerabilities, inequalities and adjacent social-economic fragilities. With this aim in mind, we have studied the case of the strategy towards a low-carbon Belgium. More specifically, we have carried out an analysis of existing institutional low-carbon scenarios exercises. These artifacts, which are situated at the interface between science and policy, are taken as an entry point for exploring the linkages between social and ecological objectives into low-carbon transition processes. Seven energy foresight studies carried out for Belgium were examined through a capability-based framework allowing to assess the way low-carbon scenarios address distributional, recognition and procedural justice. The analysis reveals that justice issues are hardly addressed in the exploration of low-carbon transition pathways. The potential conflicts and synergies between low-carbon strategies and social justice objectives are actually not taken into consideration – or only in a very limited way – in the scenario analyses reviewed. In the cases where these interactions are considered, we note that the analysis is often limited to distributional justice issues. Recognition and procedural justice are indeed missing in almost all the analysis – which is particularly problematic, since misrecognition and procedural injustice are not only injustices *per se*, but also foundations for distributional injustice. The paper concludes by emphasizing the importance of conducting low-carbon scenario exercises based on mixed methods acknowledging and coping with the pluralist needs, values, issues and solutions in order to ensure a just transition. In this sense, it is necessary to develop and experiment innovative participative approaches involving all the actors concerned by problem, including the ones representing the most vulnerable persons.

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1. Introduction

With a view to achieving the 2°C objective anchored in the Paris Agreement, the global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions will have to be reduced by around 40-70% by 2050 compared to 2010 level (IPCC 2014a). The **transition to a low-carbon society** requires to deeply rethink building, transport, industry, energy production, land use and food systems. Societal changes of this magnitude can only be achieved through ambitious long-term oriented policies supported by society at large. It is in this context that many States, including Belgium, have started to set GHG emission reduction targets, to draw up their 2050 low-carbon roadmaps and to implement mitigation policies. Besides the discussions on the (non-)effectiveness of low-carbon strategies in relation to the climate emergency (Aykut and Dahan 2016), the question arises of whether these strategies are socially just. **GHG emissions reduction policies can indeed not only exacerbate existing social inequalities, but also engender unprecedented forms of inequality** (McCauley et al. 2019; Forsyth 2014; Bauler and Fransolet 2014; Bauler et al. 2011). **These social impacts can potentially combine and reinforce each other to create double or even triple vulnerabilities** (Bauler et al. 2011). McCauley et al. explain that *“the new injustices of the low carbon energy transition are only emerging, many of which are not yet evident to policymakers or researchers”* (McCauley et al. 2019, p. 916). Interactions between ecological and social justice objectives as part of low-carbon transition processes are actually very complex and uncertain, and deserve particular attention (Williams and Doyon 2019; Jasanoff 2018; Sovacool and Dworkin 2015; Forsyth 2014). It is necessary to *“critically examining who is (and who is not) part of these processes, who wins and who loses, and recognizing the historical exclusion of peoples and worldviews”* (Williams and Doyon 2019, p. 144) in order to ensure a **just transition**. From a normative perspective, ensuring a just transition is essential because an unjust transition is not sustainable. Moreover, from a purely instrumental point of view, a low-carbon strategy that does not take social justice issues into account can potentially result in strong resistances from actors who considers themselves prejudiced, which can constitute an impediment to successful implementation of the strategy in question (Williams and Doyon 2019).

The objective of the present paper is to explore **whether and how low-carbon transition processes take into account social justice issues**. It aims to identify and analyze low-carbon transition processes' sensitivity to vulnerabilities, inequalities and adjacent social-economic fragilities. With this aim in mind, we have studied the **case of the strategy towards a low-carbon Belgium**. More specifically, we have carried out an **analysis of existing institutional low-carbon scenarios exercises**. These artifacts, which are situated at the interface between science and policy, are taken as an entry point for exploring the linkages between social and ecological objectives into low-carbon transition processes. The next section of the paper provides a review of the literature on justice in low-carbon transition processes and presents the capabilities approach as a framework for integrating distributional, recognition and procedural justice. We then move on to a methodological note. In this note, the cases selected as well as the framework for analyzing how low-carbon scenarios address justice issues are introduced. The fourth section is devoted to the case study. Following a brief presentation of the contextual background, the results of the analysis of the low-carbon scenarios exercises are outlined. The paper concludes with a discussion of the key lessons learnt from the case study.

2. Exploring Justice in Low-Carbon Transition Processes

2.1. Towards an Integrated Just Transition Framework

As part of the present paper, **justice** is understood as a *“fair, equitable, and respectful treatment of humans, other species, and the environment”* (Williams and Doyon 2019). A **just transition** can therefore be defined as a fair, equitable and respectful process of moving towards a low- or zero-carbon society (Heffron and McCauley 2018). This concept is not new. It was initially developed in the 1980’s by global trade movements as a mobilizing term for promoting “green” jobs. Despite its growing popularity among civil society, the concept of just transition has hardly percolate in academic circles (McCauley and Heffron 2018). However, this doesn’t imply that the questions of justice in low-carbon transition processes are not addressed in the literature. These questions have been addressed by various strands of literature, as shown by Williams and Doyon (2019) who explore how the interactions between low-carbon and justice are taken into consideration by different bodies of literature. The three major scholarships dealing with the questions of justice in low-carbon transition processes are **climate, energy and environmental justice literatures**. These three research areas conceptualize justice for transitions in distinct ways and focus on different facets of the problem (Williams and Doyon 2019; Heffron and McCauley 2018; Jenkins 2018; McCauley and Heffron 2018; Heffron and McCauley 2017; McCauley et al. 2013).

The concept of **environmental justice** emerged in the late 1970’s in North America. It was initially used by social movements to denounce the unequal distribution of environmental damages and associated risks in the USA, which tended to affect the most poor black and minority ethnic (Jenkins 2018; Evans and Phelan 2016; Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015; McCauley et al. 2013; Schlosberg 2007). At that time, the environmental justice discourse *“focused on local, activism-led, community-oriented means of ensuring the just distribution of toxic burdens”* (Jenkins 2018, p. 118). The concept has since evolved to cover a broader spectrum of issues than the question of the distribution of local environmental nuisances and pollution. This includes problems such as inequalities of access to urbanity, living environment, transport, health and food, as well as inequalities of participation and interpellation of public action on the experienced inequalities (Laigle 2018; Jenkins 2018; Schlosberg 2007). The concept of environmental justice has also progressively expanded from a social movement discourse to a policy vocabulary and a research area. Despite these developments, the concept is quite criticized among the literature (Jenkins 2018). Some authors consider that the environmental justice research still **hardly addresses the issues of access to energy and technologies** (Williams and Doyon 2019; Jenkins 2018). Other also claim that it tends to remain **US- or EU-centric** (Jenkins 2018). Environmental justice is further criticized for its **lack of strong conceptual basis** (Heffron and McCauley 2018; Jenkins 2018; Heffron and McCauley 2017; Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015; Schlosberg 2007). Schlosberg explains that *“the diversity of concerns in environmental justice movements has been reflected in a broad and pluralistic definition of justice used”* (Schlosberg 2013). A diversity of conceptions of justice can be observed within the social movements organizing around environmental justice, but also within the scholarships dealing with this question. The researchers are indeed influenced by social movements in defining their own definition of environmental justice (Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015; Schlosberg 2007).

The concept of **climate justice** emerged in the 1990’s and evolved alongside environmental justice (Williams and Doyon 2019; Jenkins 2018; Heffron and McCauley 2017)11/6/2019 11:50:00 AM. Just like environmental justice, it diffused from activist movements discourses to research agendas. These movements initially fight for helping people affected by climate change, for sharing the burdens and benefits of climate change, mitigation and adaptation, but also for diminishing GHG emissions (Jenkins 2018; Heffron and McCauley 2017). By *“(1) asking who benefits from CO₂ emissions and how should they bear the burden for mitigation, (2) recognizing the vast divergence in capabilities to respond to global climate change, and (3) addressing the issue of adaptation, the burdens of which are unequally focused on the world’s poor”*, the concept of climate justice deals with the “triple inequity” of

mitigation, responsibility and vulnerability associated with climate crisis (Jenkins 2018, p. 118). It **gives attention to issues that are not or hardly addressed in environmental justice community, namely justice for people in developing countries and future generations**. The concept of climate justice is actually often used as a frame for highlighting and tackling the major challenges posed by climate change to inhabitants of southern countries and or small island States (McCauley and Heffron 2018). These populations are indeed the main victims of the previously mentioned “triple inequity” of mitigation, responsibility and vulnerability. By emphasizing the temporal variation of impact and the risks to future generation, climate justice also deals with intergenerational responsibility (McCauley et al. 2013). Climate justice does however only offer a **limited comprehension of just transition where Global South and climate change concerns dominate** (McCauley and Heffron 2018). Just like environmental justice, the concept of climate justice also suffers from the **absence of consistent conceptual basis**. Various interpretations of climate justice are indeed observed across disciplines (Heffron and McCauley 2017; Jenkins 2018).

Energy justice is the more recent concept (Heffron and McCauley 2018). Unlike environmental and climate justice, energy justice has virtually no “activist past”. With a few exceptions, this term is not frequently and explicitly used by activist movements (Jenkins 2018; Heffron and McCauley 2017). The concept of energy justice started to become an object of study in early 2013. Since then, it gained more and more attention in academic circles (Heffron and McCauley 2017). This branch of literature focuses on justice issues across the energy life-cycle (from cradle to grave), both from a production- and consumption-based perspective (Heffron and McCauley 2018; McCauley and Heffron 2018). It deals with issues such as the distribution of burdens of the energy system, the access to modern energy devices, infrastructures and services, as well as the representation and inclusiveness in the energy decision-making processes (McCauley et al. 2019; Sovacool et al. 2017; Sovacool and Dworkin 2015). While environmental and climate justice are mainly based on a socio-ecological approach, energy justice **introduces a socio-technical perspective on transition justice** (Williams and Doyon 2019). However, a shortcoming of energy justice literature is that it is **dominated by Western theorists and anthropocentric concepts**. Research on energy justice have been carried out almost exclusively by European and American thinkers and tend to focus on protecting humans, but not other forms of life (McCauley et al. 2019; Sovacool et al. 2017). Yet, in light of the major impacts of current energy system upon the nature, it is necessary to go beyond anthropocentric conceptions of justice in order to tackle the issues of justice to non-human world or inter-species equity (Sovacool et al. 2017; Wallenborn 2016; Sovacool and Dworkin 2015; Schlosberg 2007). Another limitation of energy justice literature in dealing with the questions of justice in low-carbon transition is that it is limited to energy system. It does therefore **not consider non-energy sources of (in-)justice** (Jenkins 2018).

In light of the respective strengths and limitations of each approach, several researchers call for developing **a more inclusive framework based on climate, energy and environmental justice literatures** (Williams and Doyon 2019; Heffron and McCauley 2018; McCauley and Heffron 2018). Such integratory work is particularly challenging because of the diversity of the understandings of the concept of justice between climate, energy and environmental justice communities, but also within each community. The work for linking these three justice communities are still in their infancy – very few contributions being currently available. A particularly interesting attempt to unite climate, energy and environmental justice is the “JUST” Framework developed by Heffron and McCauley (2018). Based on a legal geography approach, the authors connect the three justice approaches via the spatial and temporal dimensions. As shown in the figure below [Figure 1], the JUST Framework consider that, for a given event, climate, energy and environmental justice become relevant at different time and scale. For instance, climate justice is relevant for exploring long-term global impacts on justice, while energy justice is relevant for analyzing short-term local implications on justice (Heffron and McCauley 2018).

Figure 1. The use of energy, environment and climate Justice for event analysis (Heffron and McCauley 2018)

In the present paper, **we develop an integrated just transition framework based on the capability approach**. This framework integrates distribution, recognition and procedural justice, that are the three main forms of justice that have emerged in climate, energy and environmental justice literatures. The rest of the section presents in more detail our just transition framework.

2.2. Beyond Distributional Paradigm of Justice

Liberal theories of justice such as the one developed by Rawls in 1971 used to focus almost exclusively on the distribution of social good in the society. Over the past few years, justice literature has expanded towards a broader, inclusive understanding of justice. Today, justice theories often refer to a wider perspective than just how goods are distributed. Most of the contemporary theories of justice – including the ones developed in climate, energy and environmental justice literatures – consider three forms of justice: **distributional, recognition and procedural justice** (Williams and Doyon 2019; Heffron and McCauley 2017; Bouzarovski and Simcock 2017; Jenkins et al. 2016; Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015; McCauley et al. 2013; Schlosberg 2007). Distributional, recognition and procedural justice has been identified by McCauley et al. (2013) as the “triumvirate of tenets”. As shown in the figure below [Figure 2], each tenets of justice focuses on specific evaluative and normative questions, forming the “*what, who, and how*” tenet framework (Jenkins et al. 2016)

Tenets	Evaluative	Normative
Distributional	Where are the injustices?	How should we solve them?
Recognition	Who is ignored?	How should we recognise?
Procedural	Is there fair process?	Which new processes?

Figure 2. The evaluative and normative contributions of energy justice (Jenkins et al. 2016, p. 175)

Distributional justice is often associated with Rawls’ classic conception of justice since it seek a fair allocation to all parties (Forsyth 2014). Applied to low-carbon transition, distributive justice concerns issues such as the **allocation of environmental ills and benefits (and their associated responsibilities), natural resources, as well as energy devices, infrastructures and services** (McCauley et al. 2019; Williams and Doyon 2019; Jenkins et al. 2016; Sovacool and Dworkin 2015; McCauley et al. 2013).

The second tenet of justice focuses on the **recognition of pluralist needs, values, interests, issues and solutions in the social and political realms** (Williams and Doyon 2019; Jenkins et al. 2016; McCauley et al. 2013; Schlosberg 2007). This form of justice aims at making sure that marginalized and vulnerable groups have special consideration (Sovacool et al. 2017; Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015). This aspect is important because “*disparities within societies demand differentiated solutions*” (Jasanoff 2018). Three types of misrecognition have been identified by Fraser (1998), namely cultural domination, non-

recognition (i.e.: when the needs of certain groups are not identified or ignored) and disrespect (i.e.: when groups are routinely maligned or stigmatized in public discourse and cultural representations) (Bouzarovski and Simcock 2017; Schlosberg 2007).

Procedural justice is the last tenet of justice. It concerns **fairness in the procedures according to which decisions are made** (Williams and Doyon 2019; Sovacool et al. 2017; Bouzarovski and Simcock 2017; Jenkins et al. 2016; Schlosberg 2007). It requires quality transparent information disclosure by government and businesses, local knowledge mobilization for defining the political problem and its solutions, and both formal and informal forms of participation in decision-making processes around environmental and social issues (Jenkins et al. 2016; Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015; Sovacool and Dworkin 2015; McCauley et al. 2013).

The **distributional, recognition and procedural justice are highly interlinked** (McCauley et al. 2013; Schlosberg 2007). For instance, non-democratic decision-making procedures can be at the root of misrecognition of certain groups, which can, in turn, generates maldistribution. Another example is the situation where the misrecognition of some populations leads to the fact that these populations cannot express their opinions or that their opinions are not taken into account in decision-making processes, resulting in unfair decisions. This shows that **misrecognition and procedural injustice are not only injustices per se, but also foundations for distributional injustice** (Bouzarovski and Simcock 2017; Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015; Schlosberg 2007; Fraser 1998; Honneth 1996; Young 1990). Both are indeed vectors of discrimination, that are factors favoring the emergence or reinforcement of inequalities (Laigle 2018). In this context, **it seems clear that recognition and procedures are crucial elements of justice and that an analysis of inequalities cannot be limited to distributive aspects** (McCauley et al. 2019; Schlosberg 2007; Fraser 1998; Honneth 1996; Young 1990). As Schlosberg rightly says, *“we have to look at the ‘why’ on inequity in order to both understand and remedy it”* (Schlosberg 2007, p.24).

2.3. Capabilities Approach as an Integrative Framework

As previously mentioned, the **capabilities approach** is used as a framework for integrating distribution, recognition and procedural justice, as suggested by Schlosberg (2007). This approach has been developed in the 1980's by Amartya Sen and Martha Nussbaum. It focuses on *“the freedoms generated by commodities, rather than on the commodities seen on their own”* (Sen 1999, p.74). In other words, under a capabilities approach, *“we ask not just about the resources that are sitting around, but about how those do or do not go to work, enabling [an individual] to function in a fully human way”* (Nussbaum 2000, p.71). Two key concepts of this approach are “functionings” and “capabilities”. Whereas the first corresponds to what an individual can be (e.g.: being in good health, being adequately nourished) or do (e.g.: travelling, participating in social and political life), the second is the freedom or opportunity that this individual has to achieve the functionings that he values (Robeyns 2016; Ballet, Bazin, and Pelenc 2015; Holland 2008). According to the capabilities approach, **a just society ensures that each individual attains a minimum threshold for all the capabilities that are necessary for leading a life in keeping with human dignity** (Holland 2008). Considering that the choice of these vital capabilities is context depends and that individuals should have the freedom to determine the capabilities that are required for functioning in their own communities, Amartya Sen states that contextual capability sets should ideally be defined through public deliberation. For her part, Martha Nussbaum has attempted to develop a basic capability set (see Appendix 1) (Schlosberg 2012). As we will see later, Nussbaum's capability set will be used for analytical purposes in the present paper.

One of the great strengths of the capabilities approach is its ability to **connect distributional, recognition and procedural justice in an integrative framework of justice**. This is explained by Schlosberg as follows: *“Importantly, what Sen and Nussbaum's capability approach to justice illustrates is not a singular, distribution-based, understanding of justice, but a linked approach; in the capabilities*

argument, concepts and practices such as recognition and participation are thoroughly tied to distributional concerns. The focus is not simply on a conception of distribution, or of recognition, for example, but more holistically on the importance of individuals functioning within a base of a minimal distribution of goods, social and political recognition, political participation, and other capabilities” (Schlosberg 2007, p.33-34). In addition, the capability approach is particularly relevant for dealing with the questions of justice in low-carbon transition processes since it offers a framework to **comprehend justice for future generations and non-humans**. Inter-generational and inter-species justice are actually object of particular attention in Amartya Sen and Martha Nussbaum’s works. While Sen emphasizes the importance of future generations to enjoy equal environmental benefits than their ancestors, Nussbaum has expanded her theory of justice to the natural world and developed an animals’ capability set (see Appendix 2) (Schlosberg 2012; 2007).

The following table presents a **list of capabilities** and identify potential conflicts and synergies with low-carbon transition processes [Table 1]. These capabilities come primarily from Nussbaum’s capability set² (see Appendix 1) and cover the three forms of justice considered as part of this research – i.e.: distributional, recognition and procedural. Many, but not all, of the listed capabilities can apply to various humans, future generations and non-humans. Ideally, several specific capability sets should have been co-defined with the concerned actors, but such exercise was simply not feasible as part of this research. The list of capabilities has been the basis to develop the framework for analyzing how low-carbon scenarios address justice issues that will be presented in the next section (see section “3.2. Framework for analyzing how low-carbon scenarios address justice issues”).

² Only the two capabilities followed by an asterisk do not come from Nussbaum’s capability set.

Forms of justice	Capabilities	Examples of potential interactions with low-carbon transition processes
DISTRIBUTIONAL	Being able to live to the end of a life of normal length and to have a good health	<p>Some policy measures, such as the ones directed at improving the housing stock, promoting modal shift to cycling and walking, or encouraging a shift from a diet based mainly on animal proteins towards a diet consisting of a mix of sustainably produced animal and vegetal proteins can have significant co-benefits in terms of public health. Depending on how the policy is conducted, these health benefits can be distributed more or less equitably. For example, some individuals may not benefit from the improvement in health status associated with better insulation of housing because they do not have the financial means to carry out insulation work. Some measures, such as a carbon tax implemented without compensation mechanisms for vulnerable households, could even deteriorate the health of these individuals by reducing their capacity to access energy services in the home.</p> <p>Furthermore, a long-term expansive budgetary policy in support of a climate change mitigation policy may not be sustainable for public finances and it may affect the social protection and health systems if it drains resources from them.</p>
	Being adequately nourished	<p>Low-income groups use a greater proportion of their income on essential goods like food and drink compared to medium- and high-income households. An increase in the price of food and drink, for example as a consequence of higher energy prices, is therefore likely to affect low-income groups more.</p>
	Being able to live in a quality environment*	<p>Successful implementation of low-carbon strategy should help mitigate climate change, which could in turn contribute to improve the quality of the environment in which citizens of developing countries, future generations and non-humans (will) live. Inhabitants of southern countries or small island states, the ones who will succeed us, and the planet Earth are indeed the final beneficiaries of climate mitigation policy.</p> <p>Certain GHG reduction policies and measures, such as the installation of wind turbines or biomass power plants, may, however, reduce the (perceived) quality of the living environment. Environmental justice theories highlight the connection between environmental degradation and standard of living. Poor people are more likely to live in low-quality environments than medium- and high-income households, due for instance to lower housing costs or because they have less means to oppose projects that could degrade their living environment.</p>
	Being able to have adequate shelter	<p>Energy policies can either improve or reduce access to adequate shelter. Increases in heating and electricity costs, for example as a consequence of carbon pricing, could have a negative impact on the capacity of low-income households to access adequate energy services in the home, unless there are compensation measures helping these households to finance isolation works, the installation of new energy-efficient equipment or the installation of solar panels. If such compensation measures are implemented, households that currently suffer from energy precarity should be able to live in a more adequate housing.</p>

	Being able to move freely from place to place	Higher daily transport costs, for example as a consequence of carbon pricing, road pricing, increased cost of parking, could have a negative effect on low-income households (especially for those living in secluded rural areas poorly served by public transport), unless there are opportunities for modal shift to public transport, cycling or walking.
	Being able to work as a human being, exercising practical reason, and entering into meaningful relationships of mutual recognition with other workers.	As part of the low-carbon transition, some sectors, like renewable energy production or building, are required to grow; others, like fossil fuel industry, may disappear (almost) completely; others, like car industry, are expected to transform. These profound changes in the economy should lead to the creation of new jobs, the disappearance of obsolete jobs, but also the evolution of certain jobs. Labor market transitions may have negative consequences for low-skilled workers, because they might lose a job in a sector in which they are skilled but fail to secure employment in the new sector that requires other specific skills.
	Being able to enjoy recreational activities	An increase in the price of essential goods, for example as a consequence of higher energy prices, could reduce the household budget for recreational activities. This is likely to affect low-income groups more.
	Being able to hold property (both land and moveable goods)	An increase in the price of essential goods, for example as a consequence of higher energy prices, could reduce the household budget for accessing property. This is likely to affect low-income groups more.
RECOGNITION	Being able to be treated as a dignified being whose worth is equal to that of others. This entails, at a minimum, protections against discrimination on the basis of race, sex, sexual orientation, religion, caste, ethnicity, or national origin	The low-carbon transition is a highly complex problem concerning multiple actors whose situations, needs and values differ. The recognition of these pluralist situations, needs and values in the design of low-carbon strategy is essential for ensuring a just transition.
PROCEDURAL	Being able to access adequate information*	Adequate information is needed to be able to make informed choices. It is also essential to be able to benefit from support mechanisms for energy efficiency or renewable energy installations.
	Being able to participate in political choices that govern one's life	An effective participation of all the actors concerned by the problem in the design of low-carbon strategy is required to recognize the pluralist situations, needs and values. As said before, the recognition of pluralist situations, needs and values is essential for ensuring a just transition.

Table 1. Capability set and examples of potential interactions with low-carbon transition processes (adapted from (Schiellerup et al. 2009))

3. Methodology

3.1. Case Selection

As previously mentioned, low-carbon scenarios are used as entry point for exploring the linkages between social and ecological goals into low-carbon strategy. More specifically, the paper develops on a **multiple case study analyzing if and how various energy foresight studies carried out for Belgium address social justice issues**. The criteria used for selecting the cases studies are the following:

- (1) The study corresponds to the definition of foresight developed in Fransolet (2019) – i.e.: *“a policy-oriented approach assuming that the future is multiple, uncertain and potentially radically different from the present, and aiming at envisioning and exploring in a systemic and holistic way alternative images of the future”* (Fransolet 2019, p.29).
- (2) The study explores at least one low- (or zero-)carbon scenario. Such scenario results in a low-carbon regime by 2050. The low-carbon regime can be described quantitatively (i.e.: reduction of GHG emissions of 80-100%) or qualitatively.
- (3) The geographical scope of the study covers all or part of Belgium, without exceeding the national territory.
- (4) The study has been commissioned by a public actor.
- (5) For practical reason, the report of the study is written in French or English.

Seven energy foresight studies meeting these criteria were found. The studies analyzed are the following: “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia in 2050” (CLIMACT 2012), “Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050” (CLIMACT and VITO 2013), “Macroeconomic impacts of the low-carbon transition in Belgium” (CLIMACT and VITO 2013), “Low-carbon scenarios for 2050 for the Brussels-Capital Region” (CLIMACT 2017), “Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050” (VITO, ICEDD, and Bureau fédéral du Plan 2012), “Prospective study: Energy transition” (CLIMACT et al. 2015), and “What energy networks for Wallonia in the 2030 and 2050 horizons?” (ICEDD et al. 2018). Four of them are limited to the regional territory (i.e.: CLIMACT 2012; CLIMACT 2017; CLIMACT et al. 2015; ICEDD et al. 2018) and the other three consider the whole country (i.e.: CLIMACT and VITO 2013; CLIMACT and VITO 2013; VITO, ICEDD, and Bureau fédéral du Plan 2012). Besides the geographical scope, the chosen studies differ *inter alia* in terms of clients, contractors, year of publication (i.e.: between 2012 and 2018), normative and material scopes (i.e.: from the energy system to the entire socio-technical system), approach (i.e.: forecasting or backcasting), methodology (i.e.: bottom-up modelling, top-down modelling or qualitative methodology inspired by the work of the French *prospectivists* Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet), but also regarding the level of participation and actors involved (i.e.: from expert-based analysis to participative exercises). The table below summarizes the main features of the studies analyzed [Table 2].

	CASES SELECTED						
	Case study 1: Low-carbon Wallonia	Case study 2: Low-carbon Belgium	Case study 3: Macroeconomic impacts	Case study 4: Low-carbon Brussels	Case study 5: 100% renewable	Case study 6: Energy transition	Case study 7: Energy networks
Full title	“Towards a low-carbon Wallonia by 2050”	“Scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium by 2050”	“Macroeconomic impacts of the low carbon transition in Belgium”	“Low-carbon scenarios for 2050 for the Brussels-Capital Region”	“Towards 100 renewable energy in Belgium by 2050”	“Prospective study: Energy transition”	“What energy networks for Wallonia in the 2030 and 2050 horizons?”
Emergence	Publication of the EU Roadmap 2050 and emergence of the Walloon energy-climate partly at the instigation of Green party	Publication of the study “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia by 2050”	Follow-up of the study “Low-carbon Belgium”	Publication of the study “Towards a low-carbon Wallonia by 2050”	Fukushima nuclear disaster	Identification of the energy transition as one of the main prospective issues for Wallonia through a consultative process with academics and members of Walloon administration launched by IWEPS	Follow-up of the study “Energy transition”
Clients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon agency for air and climate (AWAC) at the request of the Minister of environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate Change Section of the Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate Change Section of the Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Brussels Environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Federal, Walloon, Flemish and Brussels ministers in charge of energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon institute for evaluation, prospective and statistics (IWEPS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon institute for evaluation, prospective and statistics (IWEPS)
Contractors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ European Climate Foundation (ECF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ University of Liège (ULg) ▪ Federal Planning Bureau ▪ Oxford Economics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD) ▪ Federal Planning Bureau ▪ Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CLIMACT ▪ Institute for a Sustainable Development (IDD) ▪ Catholic University of Louvain (UCL) ▪ Federal Planning Bureau ▪ Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD) ▪ University of Liège (ULg) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Institute for Consultancy and Studies in Sustainable Development (ICEDD) ▪ CLIMACT ▪ Institute for a Sustainable Development (IDD) ▪ Federal Planning Bureau ▪ University of Liège (ULg)
Publication	February 2012	November 2013	October 2016	February 2017	December 2012	March 2015	January 2018

Normative scope	Reduction of GHG emission by 80-95%	Reduction of GHG emission by 80-95%	Reduction of GHG emission by 80-95%	Reduction of GHG emission by 80-95%	100% renewable energy	-	-
Temporal scope	2050	2050	2050	2050	2050	2050	2030 and 2050
Geographical scope	Walloon Region	Belgium	Belgium	Brussels-Capital Region	Belgium	Walloon Region	Walloon Region
Material scope	Energy system	Energy system	Energy system and economy	Energy system	Energy system and economy	Socio-technical system (energy system, economy, society and policy)	Socio-technical system (energy system, economy, society and policy)
Scenario type³	Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios	Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios		Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios	Feasibility-orientated backcasting scenarios	External scenarios	External scenarios
Methodology	Bottom-up modelling representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions (OPEERA ⁴)	Bottom-up modelling representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions (OPEERA)	Methodology based on two different macroeconomic models (HERMES and GEIM ⁵) complemented with an input-output models of the economy (OPEERA-Input/output)	Bottom-up modelling representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions (OPEERA)	Methodology based on the macro-economic modelling (TIMES) complemented with an analytical job creation model developed for the US power sector	Qualitative methodology inspired by the work of the French prospectivists Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet	Qualitative methodology inspired by the work of the French prospectivists Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet complemented with a micro-economic model developed for the Walloon energy system
Participation	Many consultations of experts and stakeholders	Many consultations of experts and stakeholders + bilateral meetings	Many consultations of experts and stakeholders	Many consultations of experts and stakeholders	Two consultations of experts and stakeholders	One consultation of experts and stakeholders	Two consultations of experts and stakeholders

Table 2. Main features of the energy foresight studies analyzed

³ As defined in the low-carbon scenario typology developed in Fransolet (2019)

⁴ Open-source Prospective Energy and Emissions Roadmap Analysis

⁵ Global Energy Industry Model

3.2. Framework for Analyzing how Low-Carbon Scenarios Address Justice Issues

The selected energy foresight studies were examined through a framework allowing to assess the way they address justice issues. With that aim in mind, we considered the **three dimensions of justice (i.e.: distributional, recognition and procedural)** and the **associated capabilities** presented earlier (see section “2.3. Capabilities approach as an integrative framework”). For each capability, we defined a number of **evaluative and normative questions**. The questions are listed in the table below [Table 3]. For each question, the material (people, communities or non-human species and ecosystems), spatial (local, national or international) and temporal (short, medium or long term) scope can be specified.

More specifically, we reviewed the seven energy foresight studies presented above, attempting to determine if and how they deal with the different questions. Note that several studies are based on quantitative models. For practical reasons, we did not analyze the simulation tools *per se*, but the papers presenting the models in question.

FORMS OF JUSTICE	CAPABILITIES	QUESTIONS		SCOPE		
		EVALUATIVE	NORMATIVE	MATERIAL (people, communities or non-human species and ecosystems)	SPATIAL (local, national or international)	TEMPORAL (short, medium or long term)
DISTRIBUTIONAL	Being able to live to the end of a life of normal length and to have a good health	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access good health? How are these effects distributed?	How to provide access for all to good health as part of the low-carbon transition?			
	Being adequately nourished	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access quality food and drink? How are these effects distributed? Are compensation measures provided for the ones that can no longer access quality food and drink?	How to provide access for all to quality food and drink as part of the low-carbon transition?			
	Being able to live in a quality environment	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access quality environment? How are these effects distributed? Are compensation measures provided for the ones that suffer from environmental damage?	How to provide access for all to quality environment as part of the low-carbon transition?			
	Being able to have adequate shelter	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access adequate shelter? How are these effects distributed? Are compensation measures provided for the ones that can no longer access adequate shelter?	How to provide access for all to adequate shelter as part of the low-carbon transition?			
	Being able to move freely from place to place	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access adequate transports? How are these effects distributed? Are compensation measures provided for the ones that can no longer access transports?	How to provide access for all to adequate transports as part of the low-carbon transition?			

	Being able to work as a human being, exercising practical reason, and entering into meaningful relationships of mutual recognition with other workers.	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access quality job? How are these effects distributed? Are compensation measures provided for the ones that lose their jobs?	How to provide access for all to quality job as part of the low-carbon transition?			
	Being able to enjoy recreational activities	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access recreational activities? How are these effects distributed? Are compensation measures provided for the ones that can no longer access recreational activities?	How to provide access for all to recreational activities as part of the low-carbon transition?			
	Being able to hold property (both land and moveable goods)	Does this low-carbon transition pathway improve or worsen the capacity to access property? How are these effects distributed? Are compensation measures provided for the ones that can no longer access property?	How to provide access for all to property as part of the low-carbon transition?			
RECOGNITION	Being able to be treated as a dignified being whose worth is equal to that of others.	Does this low-carbon transition pathway recognize pluralist needs, values, interests, issues and solutions?	How to recognize pluralist needs, values, interests, issues and solutions as part of the low-carbon transition?			
PROCEDURAL	Being able to access adequate information	Does this low-carbon transition pathway provide easy access to adequate information for everyone?	How to provide access for all to adequate information as part of the low-carbon transition?			
	Being able to participate in political choices that govern one's life	Does this low-carbon transition pathway promote citizen participation in scientific, economic, social, civic and political activities?	How to promote citizen participation in scientific, economic, social, civic and political activities as part of the low-carbon transition?			

Table 3. Framework for analyzing how low-carbon scenarios address justice issues

4. Case Study: Scenarios for a Low-Carbon Belgium

4.1. Contextual Background

Due to the 1993 institutional reform, **Belgium** has become a **federal State made up of three political-administrative levels**. At the top level, we find the federal government and two types of federated entities that do overlap, namely the regions (Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels) and the communities (Flemish, French and German) (Reuchamps 2013) [Figure X]. A specificity of Belgian federalism is the absence of hierarchy between the federal State, the regions and the communities. In addition, the competences are divided on an exclusive basis between the three political-administrative levels. Therefore, a given competence can only be exercised by a single entity. In accordance with the principle of *in foro interno, in foro externo*, the exclusivity of competences is also applied in foreign policy (Happaerts 2013). In Belgium, the power and the competences of the federated entities are relatively broad and the Sixth state reform, which has been implemented between 2011 and 2014, provides for the transfer of additional competences from the federal State to the regions and communities. At the middle and inferior political-administrative levels, we find respectively the provinces and the communes, which are under the supervision of the higher authorities, depending on the powers exercised.

Even if the environmental policy is mostly a regional competence, **climate mitigation is a shared competence between the federal State and the regions**. The issue of climate change mitigation goes actually well beyond environmental policy and concerns other policy areas such as energy, transports or even taxation. The competences are therefore fragmented between the federal State and the regions. The following table illustrates the division of competences for climate mitigation policy between the federal State and the regions [Table 4]. Except for education, the communities have no real political levers to carry out a climate-energy policy. As they have a number of political levers, including mobility and urban planning, local entities (i.e.: provinces and communes) have an important role to play in the climate mitigation policy. Yet, as part of this study, we have decided to focus on the federal and regional levels.

	FEDERAL STATE	REGIONS
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coordination of the international policy (including climate policy) ▪ Products' standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Air quality
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy foresight ▪ Nuclear fuel cycle ▪ Energy production, including offshore ▪ Major infrastructures of production and storage of energy ▪ Transport of energy ▪ Policy regarding final prices of energy for the consumer ▪ Energy efficiency of federal buildings ▪ Aspects of taxation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Distribution and local transport of electricity through networks with a nominal voltage of 70,000 volts or less ▪ Rational use of energy ▪ Distribution rates (gas and electricity) ▪ Public distribution of gas ▪ Use of firedamp and blast furnace gas ▪ Distance heat distribution networks ▪ Valorization of slag heaps ▪ New sources of energy with the exception of the ones related to nuclear energy ▪ Energy recovery by industries and other users ▪ Rational use of energy
Transports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ National airport and railway lines ▪ Taxation on fuels ▪ Vehicles' technical standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Motorways, waterways, ports and regional airports ▪ Public transport and school transport ▪ Taxation on vehicles

Table 4. Division of competences for climate mitigation policy between the federal State and the regions (adapted from Service federal Climat, 2018)

Some structures have been put in place to coordinate the actions of the regions and the federal state. These are the National Climate Commission (CNC), the Interministerial Conference for the Environment (CIE), the Coordinating Committee for International Environmental Policy (CCIEP), the Interregional Environment Committee (CELINE) and the State-Regions Concertation Committee on

Energy (CONCERE). These structures bring together political and / or administrative authorities from the federal and regional levels (Service fédéral Climat 2018).

The competences are also fragmented within each entity between different political and administrative authorities. In total, ten ministers and eleven administrations have levers for action to ensure the low-carbon transition. The table below lists the main political and administrative authorities having levers for action to ensure low-carbon transition [Table 5]. This multi-level architecture is often seen as an impediment for implementing efficient climate mitigation policy, since it generates the problem of final responsibility, that is *“if everyone is responsible, in the end there might be a situation in which nobody actually takes responsibility”* (Jänicke 2015). This has been highlighted empirically for the case of Belgium by Sander Happaerts, who after analyzing the climate policies of the national and subnational governments concludes that *“Belgian federalism allows – or sometimes even encourages – governments to shift their responsibilities upon each other”* (Happaerts 2013, p. 18). A more thorough discussion on the challenges associated with the very complex multi-level architecture of climate mitigation governance can be found in Happaerts (2013) and Fransolet (2019).

	FEDERAL STATE	WALLOON REGION
Political authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minister in charge of Energy, Environment and Sustainable Development ▪ Minister in charge of mobility ▪ Minister in charge of agriculture ▪ Minister in charge of employment and economy ▪ Minister in charge of Finances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minister in charge of budget, finances, energy, climate and airports ▪ Minister in charge of environment, ecology transition, territory planning, mobility and transports ▪ Minister in charge of Local Authorities and housing ▪ Minister in charge of agriculture ▪ Minister in charge of Economy, Industry, Research, Innovation, Digital, Employment and Training
Administrative authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ FPS⁶ Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment ▪ FPS Mobility and Transports ▪ FPS Economy ▪ FPS Finances ▪ FPS Employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Walloon Agency for Air and climate (AWAC) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Mobility and Waterways (DGO2) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Agriculture, Natural Resources and the Environment (DGO3) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Spatial Planning, Housing and Energy (DGO4) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Economy, Employment and Research (DGO6) ▪ Operational Directorate-General for Taxation (DGO7)

Table 5. Political and administrative authorities having levers for action to ensure the low-carbon transition

4.2. Justice in the Scenarios for a Low-Carbon Belgium

The review of the energy foresight studies carried out for Belgium reveals that **justice issues are hardly addressed in the analyses of low-carbon transition pathways**. The potential conflicts and synergies between low-carbon strategies and social justice objectives are actually not taken into consideration, or only in a very limited way, in the scenario analyses reviewed. In the cases where these interactions are considered, we note that the **analysis is often limited to distributive justice** issues. Taking a closer look at the different forms of justice, we indeed observe that the **recognition and procedural justice are missing in almost all the analysis**. The limits of low-carbon scenarios in addressing justice issues do of course not apply to the same extent to the different case studies. More specifically, the **scenarios analyses based on more systemic approaches**, such as the “Energy transition” study and, to a lesser extent, the “Energy networks” study, which develop on qualitative methodologies inspired by the work of the French prospectivists Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet, **take a more detailed look at the justice issues**. The rest of this section presents in more detail the results of the review of the low-carbon scenarios carried out for Belgium by distinguishing **three types of scenario approaches**:

⁶ Federal Public Service

techno-economic, economic and systemic analyses. To understand the specific features of each case study, the reader is invited to consult the summary table in appendix (see Appendix 3).

Techno-Economic Analysis (“Low-Carbon Wallonia”, “Low-Carbon Belgium” and “Low-Carbon Brussels”)

The first type of scenario approaches identified corresponds to techno-economic analyses. Three studies fall into this category: “Low-carbon Wallonia”, “Low-carbon Belgium” and “Low-carbon Brussels”. These scenario analyses aim at **exploring the technical and economic implications of alternative low-carbon transition pathways**. The three studies have been carried out by CLIMACT – in collaboration with VITO for the Belgian study – and are based on a similar methodology. The low-carbon scenarios were developed on the basis of a bottom-up model⁷ representing the energy system and the resulting GHG emissions for the sectors of energy production, building, transports, industry, agriculture and wastes. The modelling exercise has been achieved using the model Open-source Prospective Energy and Emissions Roadmap Analysis (OPEERA). The OPEERA is a variation of the 2050 Energy Calculator released by the UK Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC). It is based on an equilibrium backcasting approach between demand and energy supply.

If we look at how these techno-economic analyses address social-ecological justice issues, we observe that only one normative question is addressed – i.e.: *how to provide access to quality environment?*. By exploring alternative pathways for reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050 – and thus contributing to mitigate climate change –, these analyses **implicitly address the question of how to do justice for people in developing countries, future generations and non-humans**. Inhabitants of southern countries or small island states, the ones who will succeed us, and the planet Earth are indeed the final beneficiaries of climate mitigation policy.

The **other justice issues are not addressed** in these scenario analyses. The cost analysis is limited to the investment costs, the operations and maintenance costs and the energy costs. It doesn’t include the positive and negative externalities of the transition towards a low-carbon society. Some potential externalities such as the co-benefits on household energy bills, jobs, health and other environmental aspects (water, biodiversity, ocean acidification) or the negative impacts of wind turbines on landscape are identified, but not thoroughly explored. These limits are acknowledged by the authors who call for further investigations: *“While the technical implications of low carbon scenarios are explained in detail, the analysis of the macroeconomic implications of the scenarios, typically their impact on competitiveness and on job creation, is not part of the current work. Although these will be important dimensions to account for when comparing the scenarios, such an analysis requires other methodologies and tools and will be best performed now that the set of technically feasible scenarios has been established. Other questions regarding for instance the social implications or the financing of the transition should be further addressed complementarily to this work.”* (CLIMACT & VITO, 2013).

Economic Analyses (“Macro-Economic Impacts” and “100% Renewable”)

That brings us to the second type of scenario approach, i.e.: the economic analyses. This type of analysis aims at **exploring the economic implications of the low-carbon transition**. Depending on the level of the analysis, two sub-types of economic analyses can be distinguished, namely **macro- and micro-economic simulations**. While the former explores the potential impacts of alternative transition pathways on different macro-economic indicators like growth, employment, competitiveness, the latter captures the interrelationships between the behavior of various economic agents (e.g.: policymakers, households, businesses) and GHG emissions. As part of the review of the scenarios for a low-carbon Belgium, two macro-economic analyses were identified: “Macro-economic impacts” –

⁷ Different typologies of modelling approaches exist. We often distinguish top-down (i.e.: macro-economic detail) versus bottom-up (i.e.: technological detail), agent-based versus “one-actor”, simulation versus optimization and process-based versus cost-benefit (Turnheim & al., 2015).

that is a follow-up of the study “Low-carbon Belgium” – and “100% renewable”. Macro-economic analyses are typically carried out with top-down models. While the study “Macro-economic impacts” rests on a methodology based on the combination of HERMES, GEIM and OPEERA-Input/output models, “100% renewable” has been carried out with TIMES model complemented with an analytical job creation model developed for the US power sector (Wei, Patadia, and Kammen 2010; Kammen, Kapadia, and Fripp 2004).

Macro-economic analyses like the “Macro-economic impacts” and “100% renewable” studies enable to capture some justice issues that are not addressed in techno-economic analyses. This type of analysis can indeed **quantify medium- and long-term impacts of the low-carbon transition on energy prices and households’ net disposable income**. These economic variables contribute to the fulfilment of human capabilities such as the access to good health, quality food and drink, quality environment, adequate shelter, transports, recreational activities and property. Macro-economic simulation tools can, however, not grasp the diversity and heterogeneity in the population. As a result, this approach does not allow to explore the inequalities between different social groups. Conversely, by focusing on the level of the individual household, micro-economic analyses provide tools to address these distributive justice issues. The **SUSPENS project** falls into the category of micro-economic analyses. It intends to capture distributive and ecological impacts of different low-carbon policies by running the EUROMOD microsimulation model on a the PEACH2AR database. This dataset combines information on incomes, consumption and the environmental impact of consumption at the household level in Belgium (Bureau fédéral du Plan 2018). The SUSPENS project thus aims to introduce an additional analytical dimension to the evaluation of the social-ecological implications of alternative pathways toward a low-carbon Belgium.

In addition to the impacts on energy prices and households’ net disposable income, the “100% renewable” study provides insight into the **medium- and long-term impacts of the low-carbon transition on Belgium’s security of energy supply**. The question of the security of supply is important from a social perspective since it directly contributes to the fulfilment of capabilities such as access to adequate shelter and transports. As part of the “100% renewable” study, the impact of the energy transition on the security of supply is analyzed by quantifying the external fuel bill for Belgium.

Finally, the macro-economic analysis reviewed as part of this paper also quantify the **medium-term impacts⁸ of alternative low-carbon transition pathways on employment**. In order to analyze the impacts on employment, the “Macro-economic impacts” and the “100% renewable” studies mobilize different approaches. The former runs an input-output models of the economy, while the later uses a simpler, largely spreadsheet-based analytical models. Input-output models aim at representing “*the entire economy as an interaction of goods and services between various industrial sectors and consumers*” (Wei, Patadia, and Kammen 2010, p. 921). These simulation tools consider direct (e.g.: installing wind turbines), indirect (e.g.: producing the steel that is used to manufacture the wind turbine) and induced employment (e.g.: research and development on wind turbine technology). They also enable to capture the job losses in one sector (e.g.: refining industries) engendered by the growth of another sector (e.g.: wind energy industry) (i.e.: sector shift). In the study “Macro-economic analysis”, job losses in the energy sector caused by the impact of low-carbon policy on fossil fuel-producing and refining industries, and on the power generation and distribution sector are estimated at 3000 in 2030. Identifying job losses as part of the low-carbon transition is key for ensuring a just transition. Compared to input-output models, analytical models provide a less complete picture of the impacts of the low-carbon transition on employment. They indeed often limit their scope to direct jobs and do not quantify job losses associated with sector shift. Although they are based on different methods, the two macro-economic analyses reviewed in this paper lead to the conclusion that the low-carbon transition can create more job than the business as usual scenario. The net employment

⁸ Long-term impacts on employment are usually not quantified as they are considered as too uncertain, in particular because of the uncertainties surrounding technological development.

growth in Belgium in 2030 is estimated at +/- 80,000 jobs in the “Macro-economic impacts” study and between 20,000 and 60,000 in the “100% renewable” study. These analyses further highlight the low-carbon strategies that can create the most job – i.e.: developing low-carbon building and solar energy. This type of information is crucial to guide policy action in favor of a just transition. One of the limits of macro-economic analyses in exploring the impacts of low-carbon transition on employment is that they do not take into account qualitative dimensions like the quality of the new jobs created or the type of qualification required to access these new jobs. As we will see later, these dimensions are important when considering social-ecological justice issues. The authors recognize the **limits of pure quantitative analysis** and call for additional reflections: *“The findings expressed in the different studies have to be complemented by some other reflections on the type of jobs and the context creation of the jobs. Even if job impacts can be positive overall, significant shifts in employment among or within sectors are to be expected. The implementation of guiding and appropriate policies and measures will be of major importance to ensure an orderly transition of job switching between sectors.”* (VITO, ICEDD, and Bureau fédéral du Plan 2012).

Systemic Analyses (“Energy Transition” and “Energy Networks”)

The last type of scenario analyses corresponds to systemic analyses. This term has been adopted to describe scenario analyses based on **multidisciplinary approaches considering the problem of the low-carbon transition in its entirety and addressing the non-linear interconnections of its technical, economic, social, ecological and political dimensions**. Two systemic analysis were identified as part of the review of the low-carbon scenario carried out for Belgium: “Energy Transition” and “Energy Networks”. These two studies have been ordered by the Walloon Institute for Evaluation, Foresight and Statistics (IWEPS). At the request of the sponsor, the scenarios have been developed using methodologies inspired by the work of the French prospectivists Hugues de Jouvenel and Michel Godet. Based on the theory of systems, the scenario building approach developed as part of the work of the French School of Prospective aims at exploring the possible evolutions of a system by analyzing the interactions between the variables that compose this system. It mobilizes various qualitative methods and tools like cross-impact/structural analysis, morphological analysis and narrative methods.

Due to their ability to explore the complex interactions between the technical, economic, social, ecological and political dimensions of a problem, systemic analyses appear to be particularly suitable for addressing the social implications of the low-carbon transition. We indeed observe that **justice issues are an integral part of the “Energy Transition” and “Energy Networks” studies**. A number of **social dimensions are integrated as variables in the low-carbon scenarios**. The social variables are, among other, labor market, labor organization and mobility, household income, energy accessibility, energy precariousness, access to technology, mutualization and solidarity, education and training, and information, awareness-raising, and publicity. Through the cross-impact/structural analysis, the interactions between these social variables and the other variables of the system (e.g.: capacity and potential of local production and distribution of energy, international energy market, structure of the economy, household consumption, local environmental constraints, policy mix) are analyzed. Following the cross-impact/structural analysis, alternative possible co-evolutions of the system variables are explored through the development of contrasting energy transition scenarios. Finally, an analysis of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) is carried out for the different scenarios. The **SWOT analysis concerns several issues, including social cohesion (well-being, income inequalities, access to education and culture), democratic participation and environment**. For each scenario, a number of recommendations are formulated in relation to the different issues considered in the SWOT analysis. The “Energy Transition” and “Energy Networks” thus **include explorative and normative questions covering the three forms of justice distinguished as part of this paper, i.e.: distributional, recognition and procedural justice**.

The “Energy Transition” and “Energy Networks” studies show that **all the low-carbon scenarios can either reinforce existing social-ecological inequalities or create new forms of inequality**. In each

scenario, **social inequalities take a wide variety of form**. These dualizations apply at **individual** (e.g.: rich *versus* poor persons; net energy producers *versus* net energy consumers; members of cooperatives *versus* non-members of cooperatives; high skills workers *versus* low skills workers), but also at **territorial level** (rich *versus* poor regions; urban *versus* rural areas; regions with a significant amount of resources needed for local energy production *versus* regions with few resources). Note that the territorial justice issues do not include the inequalities between developed and developing countries, the scope of the analysis being limited to the Walloon Region. In light on the omnipresence of social inequalities in low-carbon scenarios, the authors of the “Energy transition” identify the evolution of social and territorial dualizations in energy transition processes as a priority issue for further study.

By providing a qualitative analysis of the interactions between technical, economic, social, ecological and political dimensions, the “Energy Transition” and “Energy Networks” studies enable to highlight potential conflicts and synergies between low-carbon strategies and social justice objectives that could not have been identified with pure techno-economic or macro-/micro-economic analyses. **Qualitative methods allow to grasp social issues that cannot be addressed with quantitative models**. We can illustrate this point with example of the ability to access a quality of job. As said before, macro-economic models can estimate the number of jobs created and lost per sector for alternative low-carbon transition pathways, but they do not cope with questions of who can access these new jobs and what their quality is like. Conversely, the qualitative scenario analysis methods like the ones developed as part of the work of the French School of Prospective can address these questions. They were covered in the study “Energy transition” who shows that some low-carbon transition strategies stimulate primarily the creation of jobs requiring high skills (e.g.: activities based on new technologies and ITC), while other underpin the creation of different types of jobs, including unskilled jobs (e.g.: developments of new power plants in weaker economic areas). It also indicates that certain transition pathway, like the ones based on constant technological innovation, could seriously deteriorate work conditions. Keeping pace with technological advances can actually be particularly stressful for workers, leading to health problems and/or drug consumption.

This leads us to highlight the **need to combine quantitative modelling and qualitative methods when exploring low-carbon transition pathways**. Such an exercise was carried out as part of the study “Energy networks”. The qualitative scenarios were indeed modeled with a micro-economic simulation tool. The model run enables to quantify the evolutions of various economic variables like the electricity costs and the energy bill. It also estimates the effects of implementing a subsidy policy for different scenarios. The quantitative approach thus introduced an additional analytical dimension to the analysis of alternative transition pathways. The question of combining qualitative scenarios building methods and quantitative modelling will be discussed in more detail in the concluding section.

5. Discussion & Conclusion

This last section discusses the key lessons learnt from the present case study. The discussion is enriched by elements collected as part of exploratory interviews with members of federal and regional public administrations in charge of the Belgian low-carbon strategy.

A first lesson learnt from the case study is that **justice issues are hardly addressed in the exploration of low-carbon transition pathways**. The potential interactions between low-carbon strategies and social justice objectives are indeed not considered, or only in a very limited way, in the scenario analyses reviewed. In the cases where these interactions are taken into consideration, we note that the analysis is often limited to distributive justice issues. Recognition and procedural justice are absent in almost all the analysis – which is particularly problematic, since misrecognition and procedural injustice are not only injustices *per se*, but also foundations for distributional injustice. **This observation seems to apply to low-carbon scenarios, but also to climate mitigation policies** – which is not surprising considering that science and social order are co-produced (Jasanoff 2004). It actually appears that justice issues are little, if at all, taken into account in the design of the Belgian low-carbon strategy. The interviewed public servants admit that they haven't yet conducted any extensive reflection on the just transition and that, in general, the social impacts of climate mitigation policies are not assessed. **Ex-ante and ex-post evaluations of climate mitigation policies and measures are, in fact, most often limited to analyzing their effectiveness in relation to GHG reduction targets**. Yet, the interviewed members of public administration seem to be aware of and sensitive to socio-ecological justice issues – and more particularly to distributive aspects (e.g.: energy precariousness and transition in employment). Several factors contribute to explain the low consideration of social issues in the development of climate mitigation policy. A first factor is the **lack of evaluation tools to assess the social impacts of GHG emissions reduction policies and measures**. The members of some administrations do feel quite helpless about the methods to be used to evaluate this type of impacts. For example, the only evaluation tool available to Walloon administrations is the TIMES macro-economic model, which, as we saw previously, presents a series of limits when it comes to analyzing the implications of scenarios on social justice. Another factor is the **compartmentalization of policy areas**. Social objectives are hardly — or not — integrated into climate mitigation policy, the main and virtually unique objective of climate mitigation policy being to reduce GHG emissions. This could, however, change in the near future in the Walloon Region with the establishment of the High Strategic Council (HCS) provided for in the 2019-2024 Regional Policy Declaration. This council, made up of experts from different disciplines, will have the mission of developing a methodology for assessing the impacts of every policy proposals on GHGs emissions, poverty and employment. A final factor contributing to explain the low level of consideration of social justice issues in the design of GHG emissions reduction strategies is the **low reactivity of civil society organizations defending social objectives**. It indeed appears that anti-poverty associations, and, to a lesser extent, trade unions, are not very responsive on climate-energy issues in comparison to environmental NGOs and business federations. It may be relevant to interview these actors to better understand why they have little voice on the social impacts of mitigation policies.

The case study also reveals that **low-carbon scenario analyzes are usually based on quantitative models**. This can be explained by the fact that climate and energy studies are largely dominated by economy and natural sciences. Social sciences and their qualitative methods are indeed globally under-represented among studies on climate and energy questions (Holm and Winiwarter 2017; Miller et al. 2015; Holm et al. 2013). However, **in light of the limitations of purely quantitative approaches in capturing the complexity of social dynamics, it is necessary to integrate human sciences and to develop methodologies combining quantitative modelling and qualitative methods in order to explore the implications of alternative low-carbon transition pathways on social justice** (Robertson et al. 2017; Geels, Berkhout, and van Vuuren 2016; Turnheim et al. 2015; Fortes et al. 2015; McDowall 2014; Trutnevyte et al. 2014; O' Mahony, Zhou, and Sweeney 2013; Söderholm et al. 2011; Kowalski

et al. 2009). Such interdisciplinary methodologies could indeed help to offset the limitations specific to each approach and thus “*promise to enrich each of the approaches, while providing the basis for a more robust and complete analysis of sustainable transition pathways*” (Turnheim & al. 2015, p. 239). While the limitations of modelling exercises have been mentioned previously, some limits of purely qualitative approaches are the following: An exclusively qualitative analysis does not allow to know if the scenarios developed reach the quantitative GHG reduction targets, are cost-effective, or even technically feasible. Quantitative modelling is therefore necessary to make sure that the low-carbon scenarios are consistent (Robertson & al. 2017; Fortes & al., 2015, Söderholm & al., 2011). Despite the multitude calls for combining quantitative modelling and qualitative methods, low-carbon scenario analyses based on mixed methodologies are pretty rare⁹ (Robertson & al. 2017; Fortes & al., 2015). Combining qualitative and quantitative methods remaining a methodological challenge, a timely avenue for research would be to develop and test such scenario building approaches.

Finally, we observe through the case study that **associations fighting poverty and social inequalities are generally not involved in low-carbon scenario building processes**. Most of the consultations conducted as part of the energy foresight studies analyzed bring together business federations, trade unions, as well as environmental and development NGOs. As we mentioned earlier in the discussion, **this observation also seems to apply to decision-making processes around climate-energy issues**. However, with a view to ensuring a just transition and fostering social acceptability of low-carbon strategy, it is necessary to recognize the pluralist needs, values, interests, issues and solutions in the design of this strategy. In this sense, it is essential to involve all the actors concerned by problem – including the ones representing the most vulnerable persons – in the development of the low-carbon strategy. The present paper thus concludes by emphasizing that socio-technical controversies like climate change cannot be addressed with traditional top-down technocratic approaches and **call for alternative modes of democracy based on dialogue and mutual learning processes enrolling new kind of expertise** (Callon, Lascoumes, and Barthe 2001). It is therefore **necessary to deeply rethink governance and to experiment innovative participative approaches** with a view to ensuring a just transition.

⁹ This kind of approach has already been used to build low-carbon scenarios by, *inter alia*, Fortes & al. (2014) ; Turnheim & al., 2015, McDowall (2014), Trutnevyte & al. (2014) and Robertson & al. (2017).

Bibliography

- Aykut, Stefan C., and Amy Dahan. 2016. 'La Gouvernance Du Changement Climatique : Anatomie d'un Schisme de Réalité'. In *Gouverner Le Progrès et Ses Dégâts*, edited by Dominique Pestre, 97–132. Paris: La Découverte. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01403103/document>.
- Ballet, Jérôme, Damien Bazin, and Jérôme Pelenc. 2015. 'Justice environnementale et approche par les capacités'. *Revue de philosophie économique* 16 (1): 13–39.
- Bauler, Tom, and Aurore Fransolet. 2014. 'Socialeconomische Ongelijkheden in Koolstofarme Strategieën Op Het Waalse En Federale Niveau'. In *Armoede En Sociale Uitsluiting: Jaarboek 2014*, edited by Danielle Dierckx, Jill Coene, and Peter Raeymaeckers. Leuven: Acco.
- Bauler, Tom, Grégoire Wallenborn, Sophie Némoz, and Céline Schmitz. 2011. 'Politiques d'atténuation Du Changement Climatique et Justice Sociale En Belgique: Analyses de Trois Mesures et Recommandations'. http://igeat.ulb.ac.be/fileadmin/media/publications/CEDD/KBF-CCMPsj-rapport_final_phase2.pdf.
- Bouzarovski, Stefan, and Neil Simcock. 2017. 'Spatializing Energy Justice'. *Energy Policy* 107: 640–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.03.064>.
- Bureau fédéral du Plan. 2018. 'The PEACH2AIR Database of Air Pollution Associated with Household Consumption in Belgium in 2014: Methodological Description for the SUSPENS Research Project Funded by the Federal Science Policy Office'.
- Callon, Michel, Pierre Lascoumes, and Yannick Barthe. 2001. *Agir dans un monde incertain: Essai sur la démocratie technique*. Paris: Seuil. <http://banq.pretnumerique.ca/accueil/isbn/9782021157499>.
- CLIMACT. 2012. 'Vers Une Wallonie Bas-Carbone En 2050: Une Étude Technico-Économique Réalisée Pour l'Agence Wallonne de l'air & Du Climat'. https://www.climat.be/2050/files/2513/8625/2687/Low_Carbon_Scenarios_for_BE_2050_-_Final_Report.pdf.
- . 2016. 'Macroeconomic Impacts of the Low Carbon Transition in Belgium'. https://www.klimaat.be/files/9614/8006/1207/macro_low_carbon_report_FINAL.pdf.
- . 2017. 'Scénarios Bas-Carbone à l'horizon 2050 Pour La Région de Bruxelles-Capitale'. http://document.environnement.brussels/opac_css/elecfile/2017-02-03_-_Rapport_v17-final.pdf.
- CLIMACT, UCL, Bureau fédéral du Plan, ICEDD, IDD, and ULg. 2015. 'Étude de Prospective: "Transition Énergétique"'. https://www.iweps.be/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/2014_-_transition_energetique_-_rapport_final_0.pdf.
- CLIMACT, and VITO. 2013. 'Scenarios for a Low Carbon Belgium by 2050'. https://www.climat.be/2050/files/2513/8625/2687/Low_Carbon_Scenarios_for_BE_2050_-_Final_Report.pdf.
- Evans, Geoff, and Liam Phelan. 2016. 'Transition to a Post-Carbon Society: Linking Environmental Justice and Just Transition Discourses'. *Energy Policy* 99: 329–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.05.003>.
- Forsyth, Tim. 2014. 'Climate Justice Is Not Just Ice'. *Geoforum* 54: 230–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2012.12.008>.
- Fortes, Patrícia, António Alvarenga, Júlia Seixas, and Sofia Rodrigues. 2015. 'Long-Term Energy Scenarios: Bridging the Gap between Socio-Economic Storylines and Energy Modeling'. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 91: 161–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2014.02.006>.
- Fransolet, Aurore. 2019. 'Knowing and Governing Super-Wicked Problems: A Social Analysis of Low-

- Carbon Scenarios'. Université Libre de Bruxelles. <https://difusion.ulb.ac.be/vufind/Record/ULB-DIPOT:oai:dipot.ulb.ac.be:2013/286373/TOC>.
- Fraser, Nancy. 1998. 'Social Justice in the Age of Identity Politics: Redistribution, Recognition, Participation.', 29.
- Geels, Frank W., Frans Berkhout, and Detlef P. van Vuuren. 2016. 'Bridging Analytical Approaches for Low-Carbon Transitions'. *Nature Climate Change* 6 (6): 576–83. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2980>.
- Happaerts, Sander. 2013. 'Multi-Level Governance of Climate Change in Belgium: Modest Subnational Policies in a Complex Setting'. <https://hiva.kuleuven.be/nl/backupoud/docs/working-papers/hiva-wp2013-04.pdf>.
- Heffron, Raphael J., and Darren McCauley. 2017. 'The Concept of Energy Justice across the Disciplines'. *Energy Policy* 105: 658–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.03.018>.
- . 2018. 'What Is the "Just Transition"?' *Geoforum* 88: 74–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2017.11.016>.
- Holland, Breena. 2008. 'Justice and the Environment in Nussbaum's "Capabilities Approach": Why Sustainable Ecological Capacity Is a Meta-Capability'. *Political Research Quarterly* 61 (2): 319–32. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1065912907306471>.
- Holm, Poul, Michael Evan Goodsite, Sierd Cloetingh, Mauro Agnoletti, Bedrich Moldan, Daniel J. Lang, Rik Leemans, et al. 2013. 'Collaboration between the Natural, Social and Human Sciences in Global Change Research'. *Environmental Science & Policy* 28: 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.11.010>.
- Holm, Poul, and Verena Winiwarter. 2017. 'Climate Change Studies and the Human Sciences'. *Global and Planetary Change* 156: 115–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2017.05.006>.
- Honneth, Axel. 1996. *The Struggle for Recognition: The Moral Grammar of Social Conflicts*. 1st MIT Press ed. Studies in Contemporary German Social Thought. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.
- ICEDD, CLIMACT, ULg, IDD, Bureau fédéral du Plan, and Grégoire Wallenborn. 2018. 'Quels Réseaux Énergétiques Pour La Wallonie Aux Horizons 2030 et 2050?' https://www.iweeps.be/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Rapport-Final_Reseaux_IWEPS_-2018.pdf.
- IPCC. 2014a. 'Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report: Summary for Policymakers'. http://www.ipcc.ch/pdf/assessment-report/ar5/syr/AR5_SYR_FINAL_SPM.pdf.
- Jänicke, Martin. 2015. 'Horizontal and Vertical Reinforcement in Global Climate Governance'. *Energies* 8 (6): 5782–99. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en8065782>.
- Jasanoff, Sheila, ed. 2004. *States of Knowledge: The Co-Production of Science and Social Order*. International Library of Sociology. London ; New York: Routledge.
- . 2018. 'Just Transitions: A Humble Approach to Global Energy Futures'. *Energy Research & Social Science*, Energy and the Future, 35: 11–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.11.025>.
- Jenkins, Kirsten. 2018. 'Setting Energy Justice Apart from the Crowd: Lessons from Environmental and Climate Justice'. *Energy Research & Social Science* 39: 117–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.11.015>.
- Jenkins, Kirsten, Darren McCauley, Raphael Heffron, Hannes Stephan, and Robert Rehner. 2016. 'Energy Justice: A Conceptual Review'. *Energy Research & Social Science* 11: 174–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.10.004>.
- Kammen, Daniel M, Kamal Kapadia, and Matthias Fripp. 2004. 'Putting Renewables to Work: How Many Jobs Can the Clean Energy Industry Generate?', 28.

- Kowalski, Katharina, Sigrid Stagl, Reinhard Madlener, and Ines Omann. 2009. 'Sustainable Energy Futures: Methodological Challenges in Combining Scenarios and Participatory Multi-Criteria Analysis'. *European Journal of Operational Research* 197 (3): 1063–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2007.12.049>.
- Laigle, Lydie. 2018. 'Inégalités Environnementales et Justice Climatique'. In . Bruxelles, Belgique.
- McCauley, Darren, and Raphael Heffron. 2018. 'Just Transition: Integrating Climate, Energy and Environmental Justice'. *Energy Policy* 119: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.04.014>.
- McCauley, Darren, Raphael J. Heffron, Hannes Stephan, and Kirsten Jenkins. 2013. 'Advancing Energy Justice: The Triumvirate of Tenets'. *International Energy Law Review* 32 (3): 107–10.
- McCauley, Darren, Vasna Ramasar, Raphael J. Heffron, Benjamin K. Sovacool, Desta Mebratu, and Luis Mundaca. 2019. 'Energy Justice in the Transition to Low Carbon Energy Systems: Exploring Key Themes in Interdisciplinary Research'. *Applied Energy* 233–234: 916–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.10.005>.
- McDowall, Will. 2014. 'Exploring Possible Transition Pathways for Hydrogen Energy: A Hybrid Approach Using Socio-Technical Scenarios and Energy System Modelling'. *Futures* 63: 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2014.07.004>.
- Miller, Clark A., Jason O'Leary, Elisabeth Graffy, Ellen B. Stechel, and Gary Dirks. 2015. 'Narrative Futures and the Governance of Energy Transitions'. *Futures* 70: 65–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2014.12.001>.
- O' Mahony, Tadhg, P. Zhou, and John Sweeney. 2013. 'Integrated Scenarios of Energy-Related CO2 Emissions in Ireland: A Multi-Sectoral Analysis to 2020'. *Ecological Economics* 93: 385–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.06.016>.
- Reuchamps, Min. 2013. 'Structures Institutionnelles Du Fédéralisme Belge'. In *Le Fédéralisme Belge: Enjeux Institutionnels, Acteurs Socio-Politiques & Opinions Publiques*, edited by Régis Dandoy, Geoffroy Matagne, and Caroline Van Wynsberghe, 29–61. Louvain-la-Neuve: Academia Bruylant.
- Robertson, Elizabeth, Áine O'Grady, John Barton, Stuart Galloway, Damiete Emmanuel-Yusuf, Matthew Leach, Geoff Hammond, Murray Thomson, and Tim Foxon. 2017. 'Reconciling Qualitative Storylines and Quantitative Descriptions: An Iterative Approach'. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 118: 293–306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2017.02.030>.
- Robeyns, Ingrid. 2016. 'The Capability Approach'. In *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, edited by Edward N. Zalta, Winter 2016. Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2016/entries/capability-approach/>.
- Schiellerup, Pernille, Joana Chiavari, Tom Bauler, and Marco Grancagnolo. 2009. 'Climate Change Mitigation Policies and Social Justice in Europe: An Exploration of Potential Conflicts and Synergies'. <http://igeat.ulb.ac.be/fileadmin/media/publications/CEDD/Bauler-ClimatChangeAndSocialJustice-kbf.pdf>.
- Schlosberg, David. 2007. *Defining Environmental Justice: Theories, Movements, and Nature*. Oxford University Press. <https://www.oxfordscholarship.com/view/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199286294.001.0001/acprof-9780199286294>.
- . 2012. 'Justice, Ecological Integrity, and Climate Change'. In *Ethical Adaptation to Climate Change: Human Virtues of the Future*, edited by Allen Thompson and Jeremy Bendik-Keymer. The MIT Press. <https://mitpress.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.7551/mitpress/9780262017534.001.0001/upso-9780262017534-chapter-9>.

- . 2013. 'Theorising Environmental Justice: The Expanding Sphere of a Discourse'. *Environmental Politics* 22 (1): 37–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2013.755387>.
- Service fédéral Climat. 2018. 'Climat - Le site fédéral belge pour une information fiable sur les changements climatiques'. 2018. <http://www.climat.be/fr-be/>.
- Söderholm, Patrik, Roger Hildingsson, Bengt Johansson, Jamil Khan, and Fredrik Wilhelmsson. 2011. 'Governing the Transition to Low-Carbon Futures: A Critical Survey of Energy Scenarios for 2050'. *Futures* 43 (10): 1105–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2011.07.009>.
- Sovacool, Benjamin K., Matthew Burke, Lucy Baker, Chaitanya Kumar Kotikalapudi, and Holle Wlokas. 2017. 'New Frontiers and Conceptual Frameworks for Energy Justice'. *Energy Policy* 105: 677–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.03.005>.
- Sovacool, Benjamin K., and Michael H. Dworkin. 2015. 'Energy Justice: Conceptual Insights and Practical Applications'. *Applied Energy* 142: 435–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.01.002>.
- Trutnevyte, Evelina, John Barton, Áine O'Grady, Damiete Ogunkunle, Danny Pudjianto, and Elizabeth Robertson. 2014. 'Linking a Storyline with Multiple Models: A Cross-Scale Study of the UK Power System Transition'. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 89: 26–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2014.08.018>.
- Turnheim, Bruno, Frans Berkhout, Frank Geels, Andries Hof, Andy McMeekin, Björn Nykvist, and Detlef van Vuuren. 2015. 'Evaluating Sustainability Transitions Pathways: Bridging Analytical Approaches to Address Governance Challenges'. *Global Environmental Change* 35: 239–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.08.010>.
- VITO, ICEDD, and Bureau fédéral du Plan. 2012. 'Towards 100 Renewable Energy in Belgium by 2050'. https://www.plan.be/admin/uploaded/201212190938210.Backcasting_2050_FinalReport_12_12_12.pdf.
- Wallenborn, Grégoire. 2016. 'La multidimensionnalité des inégalités écologiques.' <https://suspensnet.files.wordpress.com/2016/05/wallenborn-2016-la-multidimensionnalitc3a9-des-inc3a9galitc3a9s-c3a9cologiques.pdf>.
- Wei, Max, Shana Patadia, and Daniel M. Kammen. 2010. 'Putting Renewables and Energy Efficiency to Work: How Many Jobs Can the Clean Energy Industry Generate in the US?' *Energy Policy* 38 (2): 919–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.10.044>.
- Williams, Stephen, and Andréanne Doyon. 2019. 'Justice in Energy Transitions'. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 31: 144–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2018.12.001>.
- Young, Iris Marion. 1990. *Justice and the Politics of Difference*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Appendix

Appendix 1 - Nussbaum's Human Capability Set

1. Life: being able to live to the end of a human life of normal length.
2. Bodily health: including health, nourishment, and shelter.
3. Bodily integrity: being able to move freely, having sovereign body boundaries, security against assault, opportunity for sexual satisfaction, and reproductive choice.
4. Senses imagination and thought: basically being able to use human intelligence and creativity; this includes adequate education, freedom of expression, and freedom of religious exercise.
5. Emotions: 'in general, to love, to grieve, to experience longing, gratitude, and justified anger'.
6. Practical reason: the basic liberal right to determine one's own notion of the good life.
7. Affiliation: two parts here. It starts with recognition, or 'being able to live with and toward others, to recognize and show concern for other human beings' and 'to be able to imagine the situation of another and to have compassion for that situation. . . .' Also includes 'having the social bases of self-respect and non-humiliation; being able to be treated as a dignified being whose worth is equal to that of others.' Nussbaum explicitly notes that this requires protecting institutions that constitute and nourish such forms of affiliation.
8. Other species: being able to 'live with concern for and in relation to animals, plants, and the world of nature'.
9. Play: 'being able to laugh, to play, to enjoy recreational activities'.
10. Control over one's environment: both political, which includes the right of political participation, and material, which includes the real opportunity to own and control property on an equal basis with others.

Appendix 2 - Nussbaum's Animals Capability Set

1. Life. “[A]ll animals are entitled to continue their lives, whether or not they have such a conscious interest.” (p. 314)
2. Bodily Health. “One of the most central entitlements of animals is the entitlement to a healthy life.” (p. 315)
3. Bodily Integrity. “[A]nimals have direct entitlements against violations of their bodily integrity by violence, abuse, and other forms of harmful treatment—whether or not the treatment in question is painful.” (p. 315)
4. Senses, Imagination, and Thought. In the human list, it reads: “Being able to use the senses, to imagine, think, and reason—and to do these things in a ‘truly human’ way...” Presumably, we can substitute ‘animal’ for ‘human’ here. Nussbaum states that this capability “includes a more general entitlement to pleasurable experiences and the avoidance of nonbeneficial pain,” and comments that “[b]y now it ought to be rather obvious where the latter point takes us in thinking about animals: toward laws banning harsh, cruel, and abusive treatment and ensuring animals’ access to sources of pleasure, such as free movement in an environment that stimulates and pleases the senses.” (p. 315–16)
5. Emotions. “[Animals] are entitled to lives in which it is open to them to have attachments to others, to love and care for others, and not to have those attachments warped by enforced isolation or the deliberate infliction of fear.” This implies “thought for the emotional needs of animals.” (p. 316)
6. Practical Reason. “To the extent that [the creature has a capacity to frame goals and projects and to plan its life], it ought to be supported, and this support requires many of the same policies already suggested by capability 4: plenty of room to move around, opportunities for a variety of activities.” (p. 316)
7. Affiliation. “Animals are entitled to opportunities to form attachments and to engage in characteristic forms of bonding and interrelationship. They are also entitled to relations with humans, when humans enter the picture, that are rewarding and reciprocal, rather than tyrannical. At the same time, they are entitled to live in a world public culture that respects them and treats them as dignified beings.... [A]nimals are entitled to world policies that grant them political rights and the legal status of dignified beings, whether they understand that status or not.” (p. 316)
8. Other species. “[Animals are entitled to] ‘be able to live with concern for and in relation to animals, plants, and the world of nature’.... This capability...calls for the gradual formation of an interdependent world in which all species will enjoy cooperative and mutually supportive relations with one another. Nature is not that way and never has been. So it calls, in a very general way, for the gradual sup-planting of the natural by the just.” (p. 316–317)
9. Play. “[This capability] calls for...provision of adequate space, light, and sensory stimulation in living places, and, above all, the presence of other species members.” (p. 317)
10. Control over One’s Environment. “For nonhuman animals, the important thing is being part of a political conception that is framed so as to respect them and that is committed to treating them justly.... On the material side, for non-human animals, the analogue to property rights is respect for the territorial integrity of their habitats, whether domestic or in the wild.” (p. 317)

Appendix 3 - Justice Issues Addressed in the Energy Foresight Studies Carried out for Belgium

FORMS OF JUSTICE	CAPABILITIES	CASE STUDIES						
		Low-carbon Wallonia	Low-carbon Belgium	Macroeconomic impacts	Low-carbon Brussels	100% renewable	Energy transition	Energy networks
DISTRIBUTIONAL	Being able to live to the end of a life of normal length and to have a good health			The analysis quantifies the impacts of the low-carbon transition on households' net disposable income. This variable can affect the capability to access good health.			The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to good health. Potential disparities between individuals (workers who train themselves to keep pace with technological progress sometimes to the detriment of their health <i>versus</i> the ones who have dropped out and have resigned to reintegrate into a professional circuit whose requirements go beyond their abilities), but also between regions (privileged regions <i>versus</i> less privileged regions who face risk of under-supply of community service infrastructures	The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to good health (in relation to the risk of under-supply of community service infrastructures such as hospitals)

							such as hospitals) are highlighted.	
	Being adequately nourished			The analysis quantifies the impacts of the low-carbon transition on households' net disposable income. This variable can affect the capability to access adequate food and drink.			The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to food (in relation to the price of agricultural products). Adaptation measures are also identified (ex.: self-production).	
	Being able to live in a quality environment	The analysis explores alternative pathways for reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050. This objective contributes to mitigate climate change.	The analysis explores alternative pathways for reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050. This objective contributes to mitigate climate change.	The analysis explores alternative pathways for reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050. This objective contributes to mitigate climate change. The analysis quantifies the impacts of the low-carbon transition on households' net disposable income. This variable can affect the capability to access quality environment.	The analysis explores alternative pathways for reducing GHG emissions by 80-95% by 2050. This objective contributes to mitigate climate change.	The analysis explores alternative pathways for reaching 100% renewable energy by 2050. This objective contributes to mitigate climate change.	The analysis explores the impacts of alternative energy transition pathways on various dimensions of environment (climate, landscape, biodiversity, natural resources, waste). Potential disparities between individuals (privileged <i>versus</i> less privileged persons) in terms of access to quality environment are highlighted.	The analysis explores the impacts of alternative energy transition pathways on various dimensions of environment (climate, landscape, natural resources, waste).

	<p>Being able to have adequate shelter</p>			<p>The analysis quantifies the impacts of the low-carbon transition on global energy prices and households' net disposable income. These variables can affect the capability to access adequate shelter.</p>		<p>The analysis quantifies the impacts of alternative energy transition pathways toward 100% renewable on electricity prices. This variable can affect the capability to access adequate shelter.</p>	<p>The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to energy (in relation to energy price and security of supply), new technology (insulated buildings, efficient devices, renewable energy production systems) and energy network infrastructures (smart grids, interconnected grids, underground energy networks). Potential disparities between individuals (precarious <i>versus</i> others; net energy producers <i>versus</i> net energy consumers; members of cooperatives <i>versus</i> others), but also between regions (urban <i>versus</i> rural areas) are highlighted. Adaptation measures are also identified (culture of</p>	<p>The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to energy (in relation to energy price and security of supply), new technology and energy network infrastructures. Potential disparities between individuals (precarious <i>versus</i> others; the ones with a high level of education <i>versus</i> the ones with a low level of education), but also between regions (region with a significant amount of resources needed for local energy production <i>versus</i> region with few resources) are highlighted.</p>
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							decommodification and voluntary sobriety; salvage, repair, recycling and self-renovation)	
	Being able to move freely from place to place			The analysis quantifies the impacts of the low-carbon transition on global energy prices and households' net disposable income. These variables can affect the capability to access adequate transports.		The analysis quantifies the impacts of alternative transition pathways toward 100% renewable on electricity prices. This variable can affect the capability to access adequate transports.	The analysis explores the implications of transition pathways in terms of access to transports infrastructures and services (ultra-fast train network; hydrogen distribution network) and low-emission vehicles. Potential disparities between individuals (privileged <i>versus</i> less privileged persons), but also between regions (privileged <i>versus</i> less privileged regions; urban <i>versus</i> rural areas) are highlighted.	
	Being able to work as a human being, exercising practical reason, and entering into meaningful relationships of mutual recognition with other workers.			The analysis quantifies the impacts of alternative low-carbon transition pathways on employment.		The analysis quantifies the impacts of alternative transition pathways toward 100% renewable on employment	The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to work. Disparities	The analysis explores the impacts of alternative energy transition pathways on employment (job creation)

							<p>between individuals (high skills workers <i>versus</i> low skills workers; workers who train themselves to keep pace with technological progress <i>versus</i> the ones that are unable to keep pace with technological progress) are highlighted. Measures for ensuring labor market transition for all are explored (education and training; development of new power plants in weaker economic areas).</p>	
	<p>Being able to enjoy recreational activities</p>			<p>The analysis quantifies the impacts of the low-carbon transition on households' net disposable income. This variable can affect the capability to access recreational activities.</p>			<p>The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to recreational activities. Potential disparities between regions (privileged regions <i>versus</i> less privileged regions who do not have access to the energy services</p>	

							offered by the latest technological advances) are highlighted.	
	Being able to hold property (both land and moveable goods)			The analysis quantifies the impacts of the low-carbon transition on households' net disposable income. This variable can affect the capability to access property.			The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to land ownership.	
RECOGNITION	Being able to be treated as a dignified being whose worth is equal to that of others.						The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of recognition of pluralist views. It also highlights the potential consequences of mis- or non-recognition of certain views (revolts).	
PROCEDURAL	Being able to access adequate information						The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of access to information (through awareness, education and	

							training). It also highlights the potential benefits of efficient information (acceptability of climate mitigation policies, behavioral changes).	
	Being able to participate in political choices that govern one's life						The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of democratic participation.	The analysis explores the implications of alternative energy transition pathways in terms of democratic participation.

Table 6. Justice issues addressed in the energy foresight studies carried out for Belgium